

**TENS OF THE ENLIGHTENMENT IN HAMZA AND SCHILLER'S
CREATIVITY
(Example of “Zaharli hayot yoxud ishq qurbonlari” and “Makr va
muhabbat”)**

Kakhramonova Sabinabonu Dilshodovna

TSUULL Uzbek philology Faculty, 3rd year

sabinabonuqaxramonova@gmail.com

Annotation. In this article, Hamza and Schiller's dramas described the common aspects of the issue of enlightenment. The origins in the work were based on enlightenment and the shortcomings in society were revealed.

Keywords: enlightenment, ignorance, new, self-understanding, awareness, benefit, plot.

Introduction. Enlightenment is an arabic word that is the “miymiy masdar” (mental metaphor) from the verb “a’rafa” (know). Its meant is a “knowledge” [3:123]. An enlightened person is a person who understands himself, knows about his purpose. Society, made up of enlightened people is a developed community. The representatives of news and German enlightenment aim to form such society. The novels, dramas written during this period, have served the same, exposed ignorance. The field that promulgates new ideas of Europe and East enlightenment, said that it affects all the people, and they began to create the scenes. They expressed the shortcomings of society one after another. So, there is a need for this, the ideology of the people needed this. They did not want the public to be immersed in this stability, supported new knowledge, and in support of modern-minded.

Discussion and results. First of all, we pay attention to the creation of these two works being compared: one is the literature of the period of German enlightenment period, and the other is literature of the modernist period. From the time of the

creation of these two works, it is true that both are in the transition from one step to the second stage. “During the period of serious changes in the life of society, historical shifts (the 18th century in Europe and the beginning of the 20th century in Turkestan were the same period), the issue of educating people who think in a new way was raised. After all, it is impossible to carry out reforms in society without introducing a new ideology and a new outlook into people’s minds” [5:31]. We can also learn from the U. Saidov’s thoughts that this is the main goal of artists who lived in this period. It was to further enrich the opinions of people lagging behind the development of science and enlightenment, to educate and promote modern thinking, because writers and creators have always been able to see the evils in society and in their works reflected them and looked for solutions.

In the origin of problems in the following works, the shortcomings in society also cause. For example, the biggest factor, the main character of the protagonists Mahmudkhan and Maryamkhan and Ferdinand and Louisa, the largest factor - discrimination. The rich man's love for a poor girl, unfortunately, was not supported by clerk fathers. The wishes of the offspring were not taken into account. The father was fortunate of the offspring, but a wealth, and the apostle of the interest. We know the works in the process of reading, only the protagonist is science and enlightenment, and others seem to be left behind. In fact, it is true, the use of words like “jaholat” (ignorance), “ma’rifat” (enlightenment), “zulm” (tyranny) “vahshat” (terror) which are repeated from the language of the heroes of “Zaharli hayot yoxud ishq qurbonlari”, is the proof of our opinion. In particular, Hamza said from the language of his hero from Mahmudkhan: “O jaholat! O ma’orifsiz davlat!” (O ignorance! A state without education!) Words of protest such as “Ey johil onalar, ey johil otalar” (O ignorant fathers, O ignorant mothers) was directed not only at his and Maryamkhan’s parents, but also at the parents of the entire society. Even Maryamkhan knows that her ignorant and getter parents are the cause of all the injustices that have befallen her. In “Makr va muhabbat” it is seen that as a result of

ignorance eventually destroys the heroes. Stratification, classism and notoriety similar problems. In the work, Schiller embodied the image of a father who wanted to marry his son to an immoral woman for the sake of his reputation, who crushed the poor with a trick, through which he revealed a lowly official. Louisa's mother is also a getter woman. Despite Miller's rebuke, her misunderstanding is evident in many places. It is also known from the conversation of Maryamkhan's mother that her mother is also interested in wealth, does not think about her daughter's happiness and in the end she regrets it, but is not the closet person to a girl a mother? They imagine a happy life as money, in fact they are also unknown to guilt in this idea. Everything that measures everything with money, reputation, fame is guilty. In both works, the wealth is a victim of career and benefits described what they did. In addition, the attitude towards girls will not be ignored. It is the most painful process to be forced to marry a person whom one does not want, to give up one's love and bear all the torture and insults. We can witness that Hamza expressed his purpose more openly in the language of his characters than Maryamkhan bitterly saying the obligation and oppression brought me to this place. Even the end of the work ends with the verses below: "Oh, jaholat! Dod g'aflat! Faryod, zaharli hayot!" (Oh, ignorance! Oh carelessness Cry, poisionus life!) The victims in the work were not only trying to get rid of love, they avoid the people of ignorant people. This is a bottom society unable to accept them, they could not accept society. But they had many hopes for life and goals. Maryamkhan, who was an advanced companion of Mahmudkhan in profession, thought and science, was not replaced by a noble's daughter. Materiality is not important for him, his dream was to see the new generation become educated, to serve in the way of knowledge. In many places, both Maryamkhan and Louisa are described as intelligent, insightful and knowledgeable. They are shown s an example in loyalty, love and other relationships. Even in Louisa's conversation with Lady and Gruff, her goals and dreams are clearly visible in her language, but the scheming and injustice done to her are heavy for a small

body.

The works are clearly described in injustices of the human heart, feelings, desires of the human period. Wealth and interest prevailed over human value and pure feelings. Writers embody the people of the time through the heroes of the work. He wanted to show the face of those who are very happy and achieved.

In particular, the due's sending seven thousand boys to America as compensation for the jewels he received for a woman in "Makr va Muhabbat" brings to mind the phrase "from the head of a fish". After all, if the leaders of the state care about residents, if they are fair to them, if they are above all others in knowledge, then the state will rise. By presenting such scenes, the author wanted to reveal the shortcomings of the officials of his time. They clearly showed the officials of that time that they should be advanced in science, learning, intelligence, and justice. In order to create an intelligent, enlightened society, they preferred to start with those in high positions. Let's prove our opinion with the following sentences: "The literature of the German enlightenment of the 18th century instilled in its people such feelings as national unity, confidence in their own strength, and the pursuit of justice. Intelligence is the main issue for enlightened people. They highly value the intellectual activity of a person, the virtue of humanity, and at the same time, the idea of enlightenment. It is known that most of the European Enlightenment of the 18th century promoted the idea of an "enlightened ruler". [3:126]

Conclusion. In conclusion, it should be noted that such scenes will lead in humanity and society to eliminate the ugliness in society. The heroes of the two works above were manifested in the analysis as a joint of society and made a great contribution to revealing the environment of that time. He skillfully showed the consequences of vices such as evil, selfishness, which are found in all times. Injustice and oppression of people were strongly condemned. The idea that knowledge is a weapon that overcomes all problems and shortcomings for all time was put forward. Through the theater, the people were informed about the importance of science and

enlightenment in human life. The tragic endings of the works served as an important factor for changing the worldview of the people.

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